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Urban Climate

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/uclim

Investigating urban heat islands over Rome and Milan during a summer period through the TERRA_URB parameterization in the ICON model

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Urban parameterization
Urban heat island
TERRA_URB
ICON
Weather and climate urban modeling
High resolution modeling

ABSTRACT

The urban heat island (UHI) effect, influenced by various built environment factors, significantly impacts human wellbeing. Detailed studies and interdisciplinary collaborations are crucial for understanding and quantifying this phenomenon and developing effective and targeted strategies to address issues related to the UHI effect. Variability in UHI temporal patterns and magnitudes poses challenges for accurate atmospheric modeling. In order to reproduce UHI dynamics, numerical models account for urban features through urban canopy parameterizations. This work presents encouraging results on the implementation of the urban scheme TERRA_URB (TU) in the ICOSahedral Nonhydrostatic (ICON) atmospheric model. The results of high-resolution ICON simulations, with and without TU, are compared against observational data and COSMO model results, where TU was already well established, for the Italian cities of Rome and Milan during the month of August 2017. The main outcome of this study is the satisfactory implementation of TU in ICON, as it reasonably reproduces UHI effects and improves air temperature forecasts for the investigated urban areas. The results constitute an update of numerical weather prediction and climate simulations for urban modeling applications, while further investigations aimed at enhancing the calibration of the model parameterization and introduction of more realistic urban canopy parameters are planned.

1. Introduction

Due to global warming, urban areas are expected to bear the greatest impacts, largely due to their dense populations and high temperatures (Heaviside et al., 2017; Adinolfi et al., 2020; Ellena et al., 2023; Sangelantoni et al., 2023). The UHI effect is a well-established phenomenon, which occurs when cities experience higher temperatures than their surrounding rural areas (Arnfield, 2003; Qian et al., 2022; Lo et al., 2020; Keat et al., 2021). Nonetheless, the temporal pattern and intensity of this phenomenon differ significantly among cities. In this perspective, advancements in research endeavors and the development of high-performance computing architectures are enabling the enhancement of atmospheric model resolution for numerical weather prediction and climate simulations. This facilitates a more precise description of the physical phenomena occurring at the urban scale (Adinolfi et al.,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2025.102335>

Received 1 March 2024; Received in revised form 3 December 2024; Accepted 8 February 2025

Available online 21 February 2025

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2023; Reder et al., 2022; Lemonsu et al., 2023; Michau et al., 2023). The scientific community has shown considerable interest in modeling the physical processes of urban areas with different approaches (Oke, 1982; Masson, 2000; Martilli et al., 2002, 2015; Salamanca et al., 2011; Trusilova et al., 2013; Wouters et al., 2016, 2017a). Indeed, urban models have demonstrated the capability to capture the complex interactions between atmosphere, soil, and urban land cover, making them valuable for heat stress applications (Lemonsu et al., 2015), air quality studies (Baklanov et al., 2018), optimizing energy consumption (Sailor, 2011), flood risk management (Guerreiro et al., 2017), and assessing public health risks (Seto et al., 2012; Yang et al., 2022), becoming essential tools in identifying strategies for urban climate adaptation and mitigation (Pelling, 2011). Various intercomparison studies (Grimmond et al., 2011; Best and Grimmond, 2015; Karsisto et al., 2016; Trusilova et al., 2016) have demonstrated that urban schemes adopt diverse modeling approaches, performing within different limits of applicability. The state-of-the-art of urban modeling is mainly divided into: (i) bulk or slab schemes (Fortuniak, 2005; De Ridder et al., 2015; Zhou et al., 2016; Wouters et al., 2016) which consider the building areas squeezed at the ground and the overall thermal and radiative characteristics, surface roughness, water storage capability, and human-generated heat dispersal of the urban areas with a set of simple bulk formulae, (ii) single-layer or canyon schemes (Oke, 1982; Masson, 2000; Masson et al., 2002; Kusaka et al., 2001; Demuzere et al., 2014) which provide a single-layer urban canopy description of the towns focusing on the surface energy budget, (iii) multi-layer schemes (Martilli et al., 2002, 2015; Kanda et al., 2005; Salamanca et al., 2011; Hogan, 2019) which are based on a multi-layer urban canopy representation and explicitly resolve the complex processes depending on the three-dimensional structure and the local properties of the morphology of the urban canopy. Nevertheless, the adoption of explicit-canyon schemes is sometimes confined to offline applications due to the high complexity and computational costs (Trusilova et al., 2016). Conversely, bulk schemes offer rapid implementation and maintenance, and can be adopted in specific circumstances, such as operational weather forecast to incorporate urban effects without significant computational expense (Best, 2005) or for global climate simulations to assess the impact of urbanization on climate without the possibility for detailed urban geometry (Oleson et al., 2008). Lipson et al. (2023) showed that bulk schemes achieve good performance, particularly when coupled with advanced hydrological/vegetation models.

The bulk urban canopy parameterization TERRA_URB (Wouters et al., 2016), namely TU in the following, was developed for the COSMO regional atmospheric model (Rockel et al., 2008; Doms et al., 2011; Raffa et al., 2023). Due to the computational efficiency of the TU scheme, its simplicity and its encouraging evaluation results, the COSMO consortium (<https://www.cosmo-model.org/>) and the CLM community (<https://www.clm-community.eu/>) agreed to designate it as the official urban parameterization for the COSMO model. The TU scheme was tested and evaluated in numerous cities characterized by different urban canopy properties and climatic conditions, such as Turin, Naples, Moscow, Kampala, Dakar and several Belgian cities coupled with the COSMO-CLM model (i.e. online mode) (Wouters et al., 2016; Brousse et al., 2018; Garbero et al., 2021; Van de Walle et al., 2021) or forced with observations as over Basel, Singapore and Toulouse (i.e. offline mode) (Wouters et al., 2015; Demuzere et al., 2017). Brousse et al. (2020) demonstrated that, for the case study of the tropical city of Kampala (Uganda), the TU parameterization embedded in COSMO-CLM was able to properly capture the Surface Urban Heat Island (SUHI) effect and the interactions between urbanization and the sea-lake breeze. Additionally, recent studies over Moscow (Varentsov et al., 2021), which represents a perfect case study of a huge urban agglomerate, demonstrated the capability of the TU parameterization to accurately capture the UHI and other meso-climatic effects induced by urbanization, confirming that TU is an effective tool for urban climate modeling research.

Due to the transition from COSMO to the ICON Weather and Climate regional model, also the TU parameterization had to be implemented in ICON (Zängl et al., 2015). Therefore, the COSMO Priority Project CITTA' (Schulz et al., 2022; Campanale et al., 2024) "City Induced Temperature change Through Advanced modelling" (<https://www.cosmo-model.org/content/tasks/priorityProjects/citta/default.htm>) involved several institutes and research centers of the COSMO Consortium to implement TERRA_URB in the ICON atmospheric model. This paper presents the results achieved with the implementation of TU in the ICON model, focusing on a summer period characterized by extreme warming conditions over Italy. The first evaluation of ICON associated with the TU scheme gains relevance considering that the COSMO model, where the same urban scheme was already implemented and widely used, will be soon completely replaced by the ICON model. It is important to note that, alongside improvements in several parameterizations compared to COSMO (Pham et al., 2021), ICON also incorporates an enhanced tile-based approach (Prill et al., 2024) for representing land cover diversity and could, in principle, represent a more effective way of addressing the heterogeneity of urban environments. This work highlights the differences between the implementation of the TU scheme in the COSMO and ICON models and assesses the capability of the TU scheme in ICON to effectively represent UHI dynamics. The UHI effect for the two Italian biggest cities, Rome and Milan, is quantitatively evaluated against observational station measurements. Additionally, an intercomparison analysis between COSMO and ICON is performed, focusing on urban climate features such as air temperature, relative humidity, and heat fluxes. Simulations are conducted with both models at approximately 2 km horizontal resolution, covering the month of August 2017 with the TU scheme activated and deactivated.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 outlines the differences between the models, the technical implementation, and the setup of the simulations. Section 3 describes the methodology and data used for evaluation. Section 4 presents the results, while Section 5 provides a conclusive discussion.

2. Model, technical implementation and setup

2.1. The ICON atmospheric model

The development of ICON (Zängl et al., 2015; Giorgetta et al., 2018) was pursued by the collaboration of several German institutes, such as the German Meteorological Service (DWD), the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M), the German Climate Computing

Centre (DKRZ), and the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), to establish a significant advancement in Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) and climate modeling. The ICON model, based on a uniform icosahedral horizontal grid, offers both a global and a local implementation, ICON-LAM. The latter was intended to replace the existing system COSMO for both operational weather forecasting and regional climate modeling. Indeed, in 2017, the COSMO Consortium started the migration from the regional atmospheric model Local Model (LM), later renamed as COSMO model (Doms et al., 2011; Baldauf et al., 2011) to the ICON-LAM as the future operational model, and also the CLM Community developed and moved to the regional climate model ICON-CLM (Pham et al., 2021), based on ICON-LAM. Zängl et al. (2015) found that a particular advantage of the icosahedral grid of ICON is not only the exact mass conservation and a better tracer mass consistency but also its higher numerical stability over steep slopes, like the steeper mountains of the Alpine domains. Recently, ICON has been used for regional simulation over Europe with several configurations, both in climate mode (Pham et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2024) and weather mode (Sakradzija and Klocke, 2018; De Lucia et al., 2022). Several studies show very promising results, indicating that ICON generally outperforms COSMO in many aspects, especially for land surface variables (Rieger et al., 2021; Pham et al., 2021). The main technical differences between ICON and COSMO in the configurations adopted for this work are defined in Table 1.

2.2. The urban canopy scheme TERRA_URB: differences between the implementations in COSMO and ICON

TERRA_URB (TU), through a bulk approach, provides modifications to the land surface parameters within the framework of the land surface model TERRA (Schulz et al., 2016; Schulz and Vogel, 2020), using the Semi-empirical URban canopy dependency (SURY) parameterization, as detailed in Wouters et al. (2016). SURY transforms the three-dimensional morphological, thermal, and radiative properties of the urban canopy into bulk surface parameters. In order to properly capture the evapotranspiration phenomenon over urban areas, TU modifies urban hydrology by preventing water infiltration and bare soil evaporation over impervious surfaces. The re-evaporation of water puddles over impervious surface areas is also included in the parameterization. Then, the heat dissipation within the land-atmosphere system due to anthropogenic activities, the so-called anthropogenic heat flux (AHF), is added to the heat budget balance, derived from external sources (Flanner, 2009).

Based on the same equations presented by Wouters et al. (2016), the TU scheme, well-established and largely used in COSMO, has now been coupled to the new icosahedral grid model ICON, which is going to replace COSMO. Beyond the intrinsic general differences between ICON and COSMO models (Pham et al., 2021), there are also specific differences that could affect the overall performance of TU in COSMO and ICON. In particular:

- different approaches to describe the heterogeneity of the land cover. COSMO uses a simplified tile approach (Wouters et al., 2017b), which divides each grid element into two land tiles, one representing urban land cover and the other representing rural land cover when TU is active. Instead, ICON implements an advanced tile approach (Prill et al., 2024), using up to three land tiles at

Table 1
Key features of ICON and COSMO configurations.

Model	ICON	COSMO
Version	ICON v2.6.6	COSMO v6
Boundary forcing	IFS Analysis 0.075° (≈8.5 km)	IFS Analysis 0.075° (≈8.5 km)
Lateral Boundary Condition (LBC)	update frequency 6 h	update frequency 6 h
Soil initializations	Temperature and moisture obtained by interpolation from IFS	Temperature and moisture obtained by interpolation from IFS
Horizontal resolution	0.0225° (≈2.5 km)	0.02° (≈2.2 km)
Time step	20 s	20 s
N° vertical levels	65 (top model level elevation = 22 km)	60 (top model level elevation = 22 km)
Output frequency	1 h	1 h
Coordinate system	– horizontal: icosahedral grids – vertical: terrain-following Gal-Chen height coordinate (Simmons and Burridge, 1981) and exponential height coordinate (SLEVE) (Schär et al., 2002; Leuenberger et al., 2010)	– horizontal: rotated geographical (lat-lon) – vertical: terrain-following Gal-Chen height coordinate (Gal-Chen and Somerville, 1975) and exponential height coordinate (SLEVE) (Schär et al., 2002) (Ritter and Geleyn, 1992)
Radiation scheme	ecRad (Hogan and Bozzo, 2018)	
Non-orographic gravity wave drag	Wave dissipation at critical level (Orr et al., 2010)	–
Sub-grid scale orographic drag	SSO scheme (Lott and Miller, 1997; Schulz, 2008)	SSO scheme (Lott and Miller, 1997; Schulz, 2008)
Microphysics	One-moment scheme (Doms et al., 2011; Seifert, 2008)	One-moment scheme (Doms et al., 2011, Baldauf and Schulz, 2004)
Convection scheme	Mass flux shallow and deep convection based on Tiedtke-Bechtold (Tiedtke, 1989; Bechtold et al., 2008)	Shallow convection: reduced Tiedtke scheme for shallow convection only (Tiedtke, 1989)
Turbulent transfer	Prognostic TKE based on Raschendorfer (Raschendorfer, 2001)	Prognostic TKE closure (Doms et al., 2011)
Land surface scheme	Tiled TERRA (Schrodin and Heise, 2001; Schulz et al., 2016; Schulz and Vogel, 2020) with TERRA_URB parameterization	TERRA (Schrodin and Heise, 2001; Doms et al., 2011; Schulz et al., 2016) with TERRA_URB parameterization
Land use dataset	GlobCover2009 (Arino et al., 2012)	GlobCover2009 (Arino et al., 2012)

each grid element to compute sub-grid scale surface fluxes of momentum, heat, and moisture. One of these tiles may represent urban land cover, or not. Using this approach, urban and natural components can coexist in the same grid cell of the model. In ICON, the tile approach is consistently employed, regardless of whether TU is activated or not.

- physiographic parameters are differently aggregated in COSMO and ICON. Although the land use parameters were derived from the same external dataset GLC2009 (Arino et al., 2012), the lookup tables implemented in ICON and COSMO to generate the land use model parameter fields are different (Asensio et al., 2021; Smiatek et al., 2008; Prill et al., 2024). This could, for example, lead to different vegetation cover (see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3), roughness length, skin conductivity and stomatal resistance, but investigations on the effects of different lookup tables between COSMO and ICON are beyond the scope of this paper and could be subject of further investigations.
- introduction of a new parameter in the land surface scheme in ICON (Tiled TERRA), that was not implemented in the land surface scheme in COSMO (TERRA). Specifically, the parameter named “c_soil_urb” is introduced in the ICON namelist (Prill et al., 2024) to account for urban effects on the hydrological cycle when TU is deactivated, sealing the soil from evaporation and infiltration over urban areas by a factor of 0.75. When TU is activated, such parameter is replaced by Impervious Surface Area (ISA) equal to 1.

Among all the urban canopy parameters, ISA is the most crucial parameter for TU, as it defines the sealed fraction, that is, the part of a model grid cell where the TU scheme is applied. At the current state of the implementation, ISA is aggregated into the tile-based ICON model from the urban class fraction of the GLC2009 (class 19) land cover dataset. The construction of ISA based on a single urban class has limitations in describing the heterogeneity of urban environments. Implementing ISA based on Local Climate Zones (LCZs) (Stewart and Oke, 2012; Ching et al., 2018) can yield better results (Aprea et al., 2023). This improvement is planned as future development in the TU implementation in ICON.

In the original implementation of TU in COSMO, proposed by Wouters et al. (2016), the ISA field was derived from the global inventory by Maucha et al. (2010). In contrast, ICON generates the ISA field using GLC2009 data. Specifically, if an ICON tile belongs to the urban class of the land use dataset GLC2009, its ISA is set to 1; if it falls into any of the remaining 22 classes, its ISA is set to 0. This process is hardcoded within ICON, whereas COSMO permits the use of ISA derived from any dataset. To ensure that the simulation results are as comparable as possible, and since ISA is a key parameter for TU, the ICON ISA was remapped to the COSMO grid and used for both models. Any slight differences in ISA between COSMO and ICON can be attributed to the remapping procedure.

The other urban canopy parameters, as albedo, emissivity, heat capacity, thermal conductivity, building height, canyon height-to-width ratio, and building fraction, employed by both models are the same as Wouters et al., 2016 (see their Table 1), based on the medium urban category by Loridan and Grimmond (2012).

2.3. Simulation setups

In order to assess the effects of a very hot summer over Rome and Milan with TU parameterization, two different computational domains have been defined. Over Rome, it extends from 40°N to 43°N and from 10.2°E to 14.8°E, while over Milan it is positioned from

Fig. 1. Computational domains (ICON and COSMO) in blue, IFS boundary conditions domain in red. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

44°N to 47.9°N and from 6°E to 15°E. In particular, the latter domain has been chosen in order to avoid crossing the Alps, improving the numerical stability. The domain extensions are the same for both ICON and COSMO. The computational grids of ICON have a horizontal grid spacing of 0.0225° (about 2.5 km), while those of COSMO have a horizontal grid spacing of 0.02° (about 2.2 km). The simulations cover a two month period (from 01 July 2017 to 31 August 2017), with the first month as spin-up period and the second as evaluation period. A similar simulation strategy was adopted by Wouters et al. (2016) to address the implementation of TU in COSMO. The analysis period was selected as it was, according to the observational dataset over Italian peninsula proposed by Brunetti et al. (2006), the second hottest summer since 1800 at a national level, after the extreme case of 2003, with an average thermal anomaly of 2.5 °C above the average of the conventional reference period 1971–2000, and the fourth driest, with precipitation 40 % below the reference period. Thus, the considered period provides a perfect case study for testing the ability of TU in capturing the UHI phenomenon.

Initial and boundary conditions are provided by the ECMWF Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) model, calculated over a spatial domain extending from 35°N to 49°N and from 4.5°E to 19.5°E, with a spatial grid cell size of 0.075° (about 8.5 km). The boundary conditions are updated every 6 h to reduce errors caused by the forcing data, preventing long-term error amplification. Fig. 1 shows the computational domains (in blue lines) of the simulations with both ICON and COSMO, and IFS boundaries (in red lines). The adopted configuration for ICON is the regional setup ICON-D2 (Chen et al., 2024) (https://www.dwd.de/EN/ourservices/nwp_forecast_data/nwp_forecast_data.html), developed and currently running in operational mode by the DWD and by other national Meteorological Services, while the adopted configuration for COSMO is the regional setup COSMO-D2 (https://www.dwd.de/DE/forschung/wettervorhersage/num_modellierung/01_num_vorhersagemodelle/regionalmodell_cosmo_d2.html). This was the old operational configuration of DWD for COSMO, currently dismissed. The main differences between the setup used for ICON and COSMO simulations are highlighted in Table 1.

The ICON and COSMO models run with TU urban parameterization activated (namely TU_ON) and with the urban parameterization deactivated (namely TU_OFF), respectively. In COSMO, when TU is deactivated, the model has only basic information about the presence of urban structures, provided through the land use dataset, such as a reduction in vegetation characteristics. Upon activating TU, the “poor man’s tile approach” is triggered (Wouters et al., 2017b), and, if there is an urban tile, TU comes into effect. In ICON, when TU is deactivated, the “c_soil_urb” parameter mimics the sealing effect of urban areas on the hydrological cycle. When TU is activated and an urban tile exists, all the TU processes related to energy and hydrological cycles are enabled.

3. Method & data

3.1. Method

The two most populated Italian cities are investigated, considering a 1° box centered over Rome and Milan, respectively. Rome is situated in the central-western part of the Italian peninsula in the Lazio region and serves as the capital city of Italy, boasting a population of over 2.75 million residents. The city is notable for its dense urban core and extensive historical architecture. Milan is a city in Northern Italy within the Lombardy region, with more than 1.37 million inhabitants and a continuously built-up urban area. The urban landscape of Milan is a blend of high urban density, extensive industrial areas, and green spaces. Given these morphologically distinct characteristics and the availability of observational hourly temperature data, Rome and Milan offer perfect case study areas to assess the ability of TU in ICON in capturing UHI dynamics, particularly under extreme warming weather conditions.

UHIs are computed as the difference of the mean diurnal cycle of 2-m air temperature (T2m) of urban point signals and rural ones. The UHIs, for both the considered cities reproduced by ICON and COSMO, are compared against station data (see Section 3.2). In order to provide a complete assessment of the TU parameterization, not only the UHIs are investigated but also the dynamics of the mean diurnal cycle of 2-m temperature for urban and rural signals have been analysed and compared with observational data. Taylor diagrams are utilized to graphically summarize the matches among simulations and observations. The statistical metrics employed in the Taylor diagrams are the Normalized Standard Deviation (NSTD), the Normalized Root Mean Standard Deviation (NRMSD) and the Pearson Correlation Coefficient, defined as follows:

$$NSTD = \frac{\sigma_S}{\sigma_{OBS}} \quad (3.1)$$

$$NRMSD = \frac{1}{\sigma_{OBS}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N ((S_i - \underline{S}) - (O_i - \underline{Q}))^2 \right)} \quad (3.2)$$

$$Corr.coeff. = \left(\frac{1}{N\sigma_S\sigma_{OBS}} \sum_{i=1}^N ((S_i - \underline{S}) - (O_i - \underline{Q})) \right) \quad (3.3)$$

where σ_S and σ_{OBS} represent the standard deviation of mean diurnal cycles of simulations and observations, respectively; N represents the number of hours in a day; S_i and O_i are the hourly values of mean diurnal cycles of simulations and observations, respectively; and \underline{S} and \underline{Q} represent the mean values of the diurnal cycles over the 24 h for simulations and observations, respectively. The metrics of STD and RMSD have been normalized with the STD of observations. Moreover, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE), defined according to eqs. 3.4 and 3.5, were assessed.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N ((S_i - O_i))^2 \right)} \tag{3.4}$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N |S_i - O_i| \right) \tag{3.5}$$

Then, an intercomparison analysis between ICON and COSMO is provided, focusing on temperature, but also relative humidity and surface heat fluxes, as proxies for urban areas. The spatial distribution of temperature and humidity is analysed during nighttime and daytime. The mean of the night hours (from 18:00 to 06:00) is considered as nighttime and the mean of the day hours (from 06:00 to 18:00) is considered as daytime, over August 2017. The assessment is conducted looking at the differences between TU_ON and TU_OFF, for both models, and their spatial matching with the ISA distribution. TU is also expected to provide a deeper understanding of

Fig. 2. At the top land use representation of Rome based on ECOCLIMAP-SG. In the middle ISA and vegetation cover for ICON. At the bottom ISA and vegetation cover of COSMO. In the panel are reported name, location, ISA percentages for both ICON and COSMO, plant cover (PLCOV) for both ICON and COSMO, altitude, and LCZ of each station.

interactions between urban areas and the atmosphere in the urban boundary layer (UBL), especially when the roughness layer is modified by the presence of the urban canopy. To this end, nocturnal zonal and meridional vertical cross section differences are assessed. Then, the diurnal cycles of surface heat latent and sensible fluxes are also presented, to highlight the different effects of TU in both models on the surface energy balance, especially over different urban areas.

3.2. Observational stations data

In this study, the evaluation was conducted using station data available for Rome and Milan, including both urban and rural weather stations. The panels of Figs. 2 and 3 present, respectively for Rome and Milan, the name, location, altitude, ISA percentages, plant cover (PLCOV), and LCZ for each station. The LCZ classification for urban stations was obtained from the ECOCLIMAP-SG dataset (Masson et al., 2003; Faroux et al., 2013). For Rome, the historical temperature station data are provided by the Regional Functional Center (CFR) of the Lazio region. Information regarding station locations and altitudes can be accessed at <https://temporeale.regione.lazio.it/aegis/map/map2d> (accessed on 21/07/2024). For Milan, the historical temperature station data are managed by the regional agency for the protection of the environment of the Lombardy region (ARPA Lombardia), with station location and altitude data

Fig. 3. At the top land use representation of Milan based on ECOCLIMAP-SG. In the middle ISA and vegetation cover for ICON. At the bottom ISA and vegetation cover of COSMO. In the panel are reported name, location, ISA percentages for both ICON and COSMO, plant cover (PLCOV) for both ICON and COSMO, altitude, and LCZ of each station.

available at https://iris.arpalombardia.it/gisINM/common/webgis_central.php?TYPE=guest (accessed on 21/07/2024). Figs. 2 and 3 also highlight the differences in vegetation cover between both models for each city. ICON, particularly for Rome, exhibits lower vegetation levels and a more gradual transition from urbanized to rural soil. To account for discrepancies in height between the model results and the real terrain of the stations, a lapse rate of $6.5 \text{ K} \cdot \text{km}^{-1}$ was applied (Dutra et al., 2020). Detailed documentation about the technical equipment of the stations is not available.

4. Results

In order to evaluate the capability of the TU parameterization implemented in ICON to capture and reproduce the UHI phenomenon, and to assess the validity of transferring TU from COSMO to ICON, simulation results for August 2017 are presented, comparing both models with TU activated and deactivated. The validation of 2-m air temperature is shown against observational station

Fig. 4. UHIs of Rome (subplot a) and Milan (subplot b) obtained with ICON (red curves) and COSMO (blue curves) and compared with OBS (black curve). Continuous curves stand for TU_ON, while dashed curves stand for TU_OFF. Urban and rural 2-m temperature diurnal cycles for Rome (subplot c and e) and Milan (subplot d and f) are also reported. The shaded areas around the curves indicate the standard deviation between the stations. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

measurements in Figs. 4 and 5. Then, intercomparison results between COSMO and ICON, with TU_ON and TU_OFF, are presented from Figs. 6 to 12, referring to temperature, relative humidity and heat fluxes.

4.1. Validation against observations

In Fig. 4, for each city, the urban and rural diurnal cycles of the temperature at 2 m (T2m) are assessed by comparing simulation results from COSMO and ICON (with TU_ON and TU_OFF) against observed (OBS) data stations (located as in Fig. 2 and in Fig. 3). The observations are reported as a black line, the red line is representative for the ICON model (continuous line is for TU_ON and the dashed one for TU_OFF) and the blue line is representative for the COSMO model. The urban and rural signals were obtained by averaging the signals of all the selected urban and rural stations. Fig. 4 also shows the UHI intensity, which ranges approximately from $-1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for Rome (subplot a) and from $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for Milan (subplot b). The higher UHI amplitude in Rome compared to Milan can be attributed to greater urbanization and lower vegetation cover in Rome (as in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3). For each city, both ICON and COSMO models highlight that TU_ON is able to capture the UHI intensity better than TU_OFF, especially during nighttime, and the TU_ON results are much closer to the observation. The UHI curves with TU deactivated are not completely flat (subplots a and b), suggesting a partial recognition of the urban-rural temperature anomaly by both models. This basic urban representation in TU_OFF simulations

Fig. 5. Taylor diagrams and related metrics for the diurnal signals represented in Fig. 4.

Fig. 6. Differences in air temperature at 2 m (TU_ON-TU_OFF) at daytime and nighttime, plotted against impervious surface area. The panels are organized by city and model as follows: Rome, with subplots a-c for ICON and d-f for COSMO, and Milan, with subplots g-i for ICON and l-n for COSMO.

could be attributed to factors such as reduced vegetation derived from the land use dataset or, in the case of ICON TU_OFF, to the partially sealing effect of paved areas modeled by the “c_soil_urb” parameter. For both models, TU_ON clearly shows a better representation of the urban signals, especially during nighttime when TU_OFF significantly underestimates the 2-m temperature. As expected, the differences between TU_ON and TU_OFF are less over rural points, even if TU_ON simulations still slightly increase the nighttime temperature signals. This could be attributed to the proximity of some rural stations to urban settlements. For Milan, the

Fig. 7. Differences in relative humidity at 2 m (TU_ON-TU_OFF) at daytime and nighttime, plotted against impervious surface area. The panels are organized by city and model as follows: Rome, with subplots a-c for ICON and d-f for COSMO, and Milan, with subplots g-i for ICON and l-n for COSMO.

ICON model with TU aligns more closely with observations for both urban and rural diurnal cycles (subplots d and f) compared to COSMO with TU, which generally strongly overestimates the 2-m temperature for both urban and rural signals, especially at daytime. Conversely, for Rome, the COSMO model with TU performs slightly better than ICON for the urban diurnal cycle, especially at nighttime (subplot c). Differences between the urban TU_ON and TU_OFF curves are more pronounced in COSMO than in ICON, particularly at nighttime. This disparity could be mainly due to the earlier mentioned “c_soil_urb” parameter in ICON, which partially

Fig. 8. Differences of temperature zonal and meridional vertical cross sections (TU_ON-TU_OFF) at nighttime, against the respective impervious surface area zonal and meridional cross sections over Rome (subplot a-b for ICON and subplot c-d for COSMO). Zonal mean refers to the computation, for every latitude, of the mean value of the field over all longitudes. Meridional mean refers to the computation, for every longitude, of the mean values of the field over all latitudes.

simulates the ISA sealing effect by limiting water infiltration and reducing evaporation of available soil moisture when TU is deactivated, an effect not accounted for in COSMO. It should also be mentioned that discrepancies in the performances of TU in ICON and COSMO could also be attributed to the different factors discussed in Section 2.2, such as different physiographic parameters, differences between the tile approaches employed by the models, as well as intermodel variability described in Table 1.

Over Rome, both models exhibit higher daytime rural temperatures for both TU_ON and TU_OFF simulations, with COSMO showing a similar behavior also for Milan rural areas. This warm rural bias at daytime results in an underestimation of the daytime UHI

Fig. 9. Differences of temperature zonal and meridional vertical cross sections (TU_ON-TU_OFF) at nighttime, against the respective impervious surface area zonal and meridional cross sections over Milan (subplot a-b for ICON and subplot c-d for COSMO).

signals (subplots e and f) and may be attributed to inaccuracies in modeling the diurnal cycle of vegetation temperature in the TERRA soil model. Schulz and Vogel (2020) addressed this issue by introducing an improved skin temperature formulation in TERRA, which adjusts the diurnal cycle amplitude of vegetation temperature through the tuning of skin conductivity. However, results presented in Fig. 4 (subplots e and f) indicate that further calibration of skin conductivity, based on land use class, may still be necessary.

The results of Fig. 4 are summarized in Fig. 5 with Taylor diagrams and the relative metrics, presented in detail in Section 3.1. The exact Taylor diagram values, with also MAE and RMSE, are also reported in Table 2. In Fig. 5, TU_ON symbols are always closer to the observations than TU_OFF ones for both models, both cities and for UHI, urban diurnal cycles and rural diurnal cycles. As expected, statistics referring to the rural points derived from TU_ON (both from ICON and COSMO models) are improved, but with minor effect.

Fig. 10. Differences of relative humidity zonal and meridional vertical cross sections (TU ON-TU OFF) at nighttime, against the respective impervious surface area zonal and meridional cross sections over Rome (subplot a-b for ICON and subplot c-d for COSMO).

For the metrics considered in the Taylor diagrams, ICON TU_ON provides better scores than COSMO TU_ON, likewise ICON TU_OFF than COSMO TU_OFF. This is also generally confirmed by MAE and RMSE, except for the MAE and RMSE for Rome urban signal, where COSMO TU_ON offers better performances than ICON TU_ON.

4.2. Intercomparison analysis

In this section, the results of ICON and COSMO models, with and without TU, are compared.

Fig. 6 shows the differences of the 2-m temperature between the simulations with TU_ON and TU_OFF for both ICON and COSMO compared with ISA (first column), during daytime (central column), and nighttime (last column). The subplots a-f refer to Rome and

Fig. 11. Differences of relative humidity zonal and meridional vertical cross sections (TU_ON-TU_OFF) at nighttime, against the respective impervious surface area zonal and meridional cross sections over Milan (subplot a-b for ICON and subplot c-d for COSMO).

subplots g-n to Milan. For both models, the results reveal clear nighttime hotspots near the cities, with a good spatial correlation between the temperature patterns and ISA. The characteristic of urban centers to exhibit a nighttime warmer than daytime has been widely confirmed in the literature (Oke, 1976; Garbero et al., 2021; Wouters et al., 2016). Over both cities, COSMO performs slightly higher temperature differences than ICON. This is consistent with the comparison against observations and can be attributed to the factors already discussed in Section 4.1.

Many recent large-scale observational and modeling studies on the UHI and urban climate (Chakraborty et al., 2022; Qian et al., 2022; Milelli et al., 2023) have focused also on relative humidity as a key source of information for accounting for the effect that cities dry out the atmosphere. Urban areas may exhibit a lower relative humidity than their surrounding rural environments due to the removal of vegetation and pervious surfaces, with the consequence of a reduced evapotranspiration. In this perspective, Fig. 7 shows the same differences depicted in Fig. 6 but in terms of relative humidity. The subplots a-f refer to Rome and subplots g-n to Milan. The results show a reduction of 2-m relative humidity of TU_ON with respect to TU_OFF during nighttime, demonstrating a close agreement

Fig. 12. Urban and rural diurnal cycles of surface heat fluxes for Rome (subplots a-d) and Milan (subplots e-h). ICON curves in red and COSMO curves in blue. Continuous lines stand for TU_ON and dashed ones for TU_OFF. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

with the ISA patterns. The performances of COSMO and ICON are similar over both cities.

It is well known that the urban areas interact with the atmosphere through various exchange processes of heat, momentum, and mass, which substantially impact human comfort, air quality, and energy consumption (Moradi et al., 2021). Such complex interactions are observable from the urban canopy layer to a few hundred meters within the atmospheric boundary layer. Indeed, Fig. 8

Table 2

Values of the metrics employed in the Taylor diagrams of Fig. 5. For the same diurnal cycle signals, are also reported the values of RMSE and MAE, defined in Section 3.1.

UHI ROME	NSTD	NRMSD	Corr. Coeff	RMSE [°C]	MAE [°C]
OBS	1	0	1	0	0
ICON TU_ON	1.44	0.68	0.91	0.95	0.80
COSMO TU_ON	1.38	0.84	0.80	1.21	0.92
ICON TU_OFF	0.58	0.85	0.65	1.66	1.28
COSMO TU_OFF	0.52	1.12	0.31	1.96	1.51
UHI MILAN	NSTD	NRMSD	Corr. Coeff.	RMSE [°C]	MAE [°C]
OBS	1	0	1	0	0
ICON TU_ON	1.13	0.53	0.88	0.70	0.56
COSMO TU_ON	1.29	0.66	0.86	0.90	0.72
ICON TU_OFF	0.55	0.60	0.86	1.31	1.11
COSMO TU_OFF	0.63	1.23	0.85	1.53	1.35
URBAN ROME	NSTD	NRMSD	Corr. Coeff.	RMSE [°C]	MAE [°C]
OBS	1	0	1	0	0
ICON TU_ON	0.98	0.16	0.99	1.14	0.98
COSMO TU_ON	1.04	0.18	0.98	0.74	0.60
ICON TU_OFF	1.42	0.54	0.96	2.26	2.06
COSMO TU_OFF	1.48	0.62	0.95	3.32	2.92
URBAN MILAN	NSTD	NRMSD	Corr. Coeff.	RMSE [°C]	MAE [°C]
OBS	1	0	1	0	0
ICON TU_ON	0.96	0.23	0.97	0.74	0.60
COSMO TU_ON	1.13	0.25	0.98	1.89	1.72
ICON TU_OFF	1.20	0.50	0.92	1.83	1.60
COSMO TU_OFF	1.43	0.63	0.92	1.97	1.88
RURAL ROME	NSTD	NRMSD	Corr. Coeff.	RMSE [°C]	MAE [°C]
OBS	1	0	1	0	0
ICON TU_ON	1.08	0.28	0.97	1.79	1.30
COSMO TU_ON	1.08	0.33	0.95	1.71	1.41
ICON TU_OFF	1.16	0.41	0.96	1.82	1.44
COSMO TU_OFF	1.16	0.49	0.94	2.25	2.00
RURAL MILAN	NSTD	NRMSD	Corr. Coeff.	RMSE [°C]	MAE [°C]
OBS	1	0	1	0	0
ICON TU_ON	0.98	0.32	0.95	1.37	1.06
COSMO TU_ON	1.12	0.34	0.95	2.48	2.07
ICON TU_OFF	1.03	0.43	0.94	1.42	1.22
COSMO TU_OFF	1.21	0.53	0.95	2.21	1.65

shows the differences at nighttime of temperature zonal and meridional mean cross-sections between TU_ON and TU_OFF over Rome for both models, while Fig. 9 presents the same for Milan. The cross-sections also include the impervious surface area. In Rome, TU_ON simulates slightly higher temperatures (less than 1 °C) compared to TU_OFF, with the greatest increases occurring at locations with higher impervious surface areas. These temperature increases extend up to 200 m above the surface. COSMO and ICON exhibit similar performance in this regard. Fig. 9 shows that, in Milan, TU_ON also simulates higher temperatures (less than 1 °C) than TU_OFF, with the most significant increases at locations with high impervious surface areas and the temperature effects extend beyond 300 m in the vertical profile. The meridional cross-section, for both ICON and COSMO, reveals a more uniform temperature increase in Milan compared to Rome, consistent with the distribution of ISA. COSMO and ICON show similar results here as well. Figs. 10 and Fig. 11 present, for both models, the nocturnal differences in relative humidity of zonal and meridional vertical mean cross-sections between TU_ON and TU_OFF for Rome and Milan, respectively. TU_ON simulates a relative humidity reduction of up to 5 % compared to TU_OFF. The greatest decreases occur where impervious surface areas are higher and affect atmospheric layers up to 300 m in Rome and beyond in Milan. Finally, it is possible to conclude that COSMO and ICON provide similar vertical profiles over both cities.

Fig. 12 illustrates the mean diurnal cycles of latent heat flux (LHFL_S) and sensible heat flux (SHFL_S) for both models in both selected cities, providing insights into temperature behavior. These fluxes are averaged over urban and rural sites, as shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. Regarding the urban sensible heat fluxes (subplots a and e), both models exhibit higher values during nighttime with TU_ON simulations, reflecting the increase in 2-m temperature over urban areas when TU is active (see Fig. 4, subplots c and d). During daytime, some differences arise between Rome and Milan. In Rome, there is a decrease in urban sensible heat fluxes for TU_ON compared to TU_OFF in both models, still mirroring the 2-m temperature behavior (see Fig. 4, subplot c). In contrast, for Milan, the TU_ON and TU_OFF simulations are more comparable for each model, with higher values for COSMO, reflecting the overestimation of daytime 2-m urban temperature over Milan by COSMO compared to ICON (as in Fig. 4, subplot d). The amount of sensible heat released during nighttime over urban areas confirms that during daytime, when there is incoming solar radiation, the urban fabric acts like a sink with a heat storing capacity (Oke, 1976; Grimmond and Oke, 1999; Wouters et al., 2015, 2016). Therefore, the stored heat is released during the night, causing the increment of 2-m temperature over urban areas. These urban dynamics are well captured in the TU_ON simulations by both models.

TU also accounts for hydrological processes in urban areas. Specifically, bare soil evaporation over paved areas is set to zero, reducing latent heat flux. For urban latent heat fluxes (Fig. 12, subplots b and f), ICON and COSMO show different behaviors for each city. In Rome (subplot b), COSMO TU_OFF shows, especially at daytime, high latent heat flux values, which are significantly reduced in COSMO TU_ON, whereas the decrease in ICON curves is less pronounced. This substantial reduction in COSMO urban latent heat flux can be justified by the lack of the “c_soil_urb” parameter. Additionally, the higher latent heat flux values in COSMO TU_OFF could be related to greater vegetation levels in COSMO compared to ICON for Rome (as reported in Fig. 2). For Milan (subplot f), for the same rationale, there is still a significant reduction in urban latent heat flux from TU_OFF to TU_ON in COSMO simulations, while a moderate difference is observed in the ICON curves. Differently to Rome, in Milan the latent heat flux TU_OFF curves of both models are comparable due to the more similar level of vegetation between the models (as reported in Fig. 3). Finally, all the rural signals are close to each other for both simulations and both models (subplots c, d and h, g), demonstrating that TU is mainly acting in urban areas, as foreseen, and not in rural areas.

5. Conclusion and discussion

This paper investigates the ability of the TU scheme implemented in the ICON atmospheric model to capture the urban heat island dynamics for Rome and Milan, focusing on August 2017, a period characterized by extreme warming conditions. This study is the first assessment of ICON associated with the TU scheme and proposes an evaluation of the mean 2-m temperature over the selected cities, performed with ICON (TU_ON and TU_OFF) and, to test the validity of the implementation, also compared with COSMO (TU_ON and TU_OFF), used as a benchmark. After having highlighted the differences of the implementation of TU in ICON and COSMO, the UHI intensities, as well as the urban and rural diurnal cycles are validated by comparing the simulation results against available station data. For both models, the simulations with TU_ON are able to capture the UHI intensity and the temperature of urban signals better than TU_OFF, especially during nighttime. The employed metrics demonstrate that ICON with TU generally performs slightly better than COSMO with TU for both selected cities. The slight discrepancies in the performance of TU in ICON and COSMO can be attributed to the ICON tile approach, which more accurately represents land cover heterogeneity, differences in the description of physiographic parameters, as well as intermodel variability due to the different parameterizations employed by the models. Similarly, ICON TU_OFF outperforms COSMO TU_OFF, possibly due to the “c_soil_urb” parameter in ICON, which mimics the sealing effect of urban land cover on water evaporation and infiltration when the TU scheme is deactivated. The intercomparison analyses between COSMO and ICON models in terms of relative humidity reveal a reduction, especially during the night, over urban areas compared to the surroundings, in close agreement with ISA patterns. The interactions between urban areas and the atmosphere are also verified by zonal and meridional vertical cross sections over both cities. Moreover, also in these analyses, COSMO and ICON show similar patterns, further corroborating the validity of the new implementation. Finally, the analysis of the mean diurnal cycles of the surface sensible and latent heat fluxes highlight that, for both models and in both cities, the TU_ON urban sensible heat fluxes are increased during nighttime with respect to TU_OFF (mirroring the increment of the 2-m temperature), while differences arise between ICON and COSMO for the latent heat flux due to different evaporation processes occurring over the cities. These differences could be attributed to variations in vegetation cover and the different treatment of the hydrological water cycle in ICON TU_OFF with respect to COSMO TU_OFF.

The main novelty of this work lies in the quantification of the performance of ICON, newly coupled with the TU urban bulk parameterization, for capturing key urban dynamic aspects, like UHIs or temperature diurnal cycles of urban areas. This assessment is conducted by comparing model results with in-situ observations and COSMO model simulations. Moreover, even if the selected cities are morphologically different, the outcomes of this research follow common conclusions, pointing out that the presented findings have a general meaning. Indeed, these encouraging results position the ICON model with TU as a promising tool for performing mesoscale numerical simulations aimed at better describing urban dynamics.

However, a limitation of this study is that the analysis focuses on a summer period and is based on a limited set of measured variables. Consequently, the assessment against observations is restricted to 2-m temperature data, and while other analysed urban climate variables are recommended for modeling investigations, they may not yet be suitable for applied studies. Therefore, this work represents an initial step toward a more comprehensive evaluation of the TU scheme in ICON. Nevertheless, several upcoming initiatives, in which ICON with the TU scheme has been selected as an urbanized regional model, will provide further opportunities for evaluation. These initiatives, which focus on weather and climate timescales, aim to investigate not only additional key variables but also different climate conditions. For instance, the Research Demonstration Project (RDP) Paris 2024 Olympics, supported by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), seeks to advance high-resolution (100 m) urban forecast systems. Similarly, the Flagship Pilot Study URBan environments and Regional Climate Change (URB-RCC) (Langendijk et al., 2024), supported by the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) and by the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) community, explores the mutual impacts of urban areas and regional climate change through coordinated model experiments. Additionally, another notable example can be the Climate-Resilient Development Pathways in Metropolitan Regions of Europe (CARMINE) project, which emphasizes the role of enhanced high-resolution urban modeling outputs in supporting tangible local adaptation and mitigation strategies. Together, all these research programs will not only strengthen the evaluation of ICON with TU but also broaden its applicability across varying urban and climatic settings.

Finally, it should be noted that with ICON having replaced COSMO as regional atmospheric model for weather and climate applications, all future development efforts, including for example enhancements to model parameterizations, optimization of configuration parameters, improvements to Urban Canopy parameters, incorporation of Local Climate Zones, will be entirely devoted on ICON. This transition offers ongoing opportunities for further refinement and advancements of ICON.

Funding

Financial support from ICSC–Centro Nazionale di Ricerca in “High Performance Computing, Big Data and Quantum Computing”, funded by European Union-NextGenerationEU (Project name: PNRH-HPC; Project number: CN00000013; CUP: C83C22000560007) and from the European Union HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions under grant agreement No 101137851, project CARMINE (Climate-Resilient Development Pathways in Metropolitan Regions of Europe, <https://www.carmine-project.eu/>).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Angelo Campanale: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marianna Adinolfi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Mario Raffa:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software, Methodology. **Jan-Peter Schulz:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation. **Paola Mercogliano:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors sincerely thank all the members of the COSMO Priority Project CITTA’ (City Induced Temperature change Through Advanced modeling), the COSMO Consortium and the CLM Community for providing support, fruitful collaborations and sharing of ideas and knowledge. The simulations were conducted on the Supercomputer JUNO (<https://www.cmcc.it/it/research/super-computing-center-scc>), housed at the Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC). The authors acknowledge the user supporting team of JUNO for providing technical assistance. The authors are grateful to all the ICON development team for providing and keeping constantly maintained the ICON source code. Finally, we acknowledge the CFR of the Lazio region (<https://protezionecivile.regione.lazio.it/gestione-emergenze/centro-funzionale>) and ARPA Lombardia (<https://www.arpalombardia.it/>) for providing weather stations data for Rome and Milan, respectively.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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